

wasteless

Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress

VIMOSZ

D7.2 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Date: 2023.06.22

Doc. Version: 1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Action (HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01) under Grant Agreement No. 101084222. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA) can be held responsible for them.

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NB OF PAGES	LEAD RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	DIFFUSION
31	<p>VIMOSZ HUNGARIAN HOSPITALITY EMPLOYERS ASSOCIATION</p>	Public

Project information

Project Acronym:	WASTELESS
Project Full Title:	Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress
Grant Agreement:	101084222
Project Duration:	36 Months (January 2023 - December 2025)
Project Coordinator:	UTAD
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Deliverable information

Deliverable Status:	draft
Deliverable Title:	D7.2 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
Deliverable Nature:	R – Document, report
Dissemination Level:	PU - public
Due Date:	M6 (30/06/2023)
Submission Date:	M6 (22/06/2023)
Work Package (WP):	7
Deliverable Leader:	VIMOSZ
Deliverable approved by the WP leader/ CO	IFA/UTAD
File Name:	03.Deliverable_7.2 WASTELESS.22-06-2023.V1.0

History of changes

Version	Date	Author	Comments	Stage
V0.1	18/01/2023	VIMOSZ	First draft/Guidelines from WP leaders for the draft structure	Draft
V0.2	08/03/2023	VIMOSZ	[Second draft]	Draft
V0.3	21/03/2023	UTAD and EuroFIR	Third draft/ contributions from WP7 partners	Draft
V0.4	30/05/2023	IFA	[Peer review]	Draft
V0.5	10/06/2023	SDU (Wu Chen)	[Peer review from WP1 leader]	Draft
V0.6	12/06/2023	IFA	[contributions from WP1 leader]	Draft
V0.7	21/06/2023	UTAD and IFA	[Final draft]	Draft
V1.0	22/06/2023	UTAD	[Final approval and submission to the E.C.]	Final

Executive Summary

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan - (D7.2) is part of the work carried out under Work Package (WP) 7, WP7, supporting, and emphasising the activities and outcomes of the project. The strategic document is to be used as a roadmap for a timely and effective implementation of project DEC activities to ensure visibility of the project and engagement of all stakeholders. This deliverable defines WASTELESS's overall DEC strategy as it is understood by the authors, in Month 6 (M6) of the project. The document i) outlines the communication objectives, identifies the main target audience, and defines key messages to convey, ii) determines the resources needed, channels (including potential cooperation with information multipliers and stakeholder networks) and tools to be used for DEC activities and iii) ensures European Union (EU) funding visibility and defines the monitoring, evaluation, and reporting procedures; all with the aim to guarantee a coherent DEC across the partnership.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CoP	Community of Practice
DC	Dissemination and Communication
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EN	English
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPPS	Intellectual Property Protection Strategy
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MS	Member States
RD	Research and Development
SoMe	Social Media
SoPs	Standard Operation Procedures
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The EU wastes annually around 88 million tonnes of food, at an estimated cost of €143 billion (FAO, 2011¹, 2019²) with tremendous negative impacts on society, the environment, and the economy. The Commission is committed to halving *per capita* food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030 in line with the Sustainable Development Goals Target 12.3 (UN, 2015). The approach is the Farm2Fork strategy, at the hearth of the European Green Deal priorities. WASTELESS project (2023-2025) aims to develop tools and recommendations for measuring and monitoring Food Loss and Waste (FLW), which will ultimately contribute to its reduction by at least 20% annually. Additionally, WASTELESS will carry research activities on innovative processes and streams to valorise unavoidable FLW.

To expand WASTELESS impact this Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan (D7.2) is a support document to build the project's DEC strategy and the roadmap to put it in place. It will be used to make the results public (dissemination), to make concrete use of the results achieved (exploitation) and to promote the project and its results (communication). This plan describes the objectives of DEC, according to the European Commission (EC) guidelines (section 2) and the project objectives and outcomes to which the DEC strategy needs to look and base its actions on (section 3), identifies the target audiences (section 4), and describes in detail the dissemination and communication (DC) channels and tools (section 5), as well as the key messages (section 6) related to the outcomes and respective audiences and defines their Key Performance Indicators (KPIs, Annex I). Additionally, the exploitation strategy (section 7), the roadmap of DEC activities (section 8) and the procedures for their monitoring, evaluation, and reporting (section 9) are included.

WP7 will lead the multidisciplinary WASTELESS partners (29 organisations from 14 countries) to invest in communicating and disseminating the project and its results (Annex II), and make concrete use of their results. The execution of the DEC plan will be tracked through its work plan and adapted throughout the project lifetime, D7.3 DEC Plan – Update (due M18) and D7.4 DEC Plan – Final report (due M36). The DEC plan will guide all WASTELESS partners, and if followed will produce the project impact defined in the Grant Agreement (GA).

¹ FAO. 2011. [Global food losses and food waste – Extent, causes and prevention](#). Rome

² FAO. 2019. [The State of Food and Agriculture 2019. Moving forward on food loss and waste reduction](#). Rome.

2. Dissemination, exploitation, and communication objectives

Dissemination, exploitation, and communication are a legal obligation of HORIZON projects to maximise the project impact. There is a legal obligation to share research results with the scientific community, commercial players, civil society, and policymakers (dissemination and communication), and to take action to use project results for commercial purposes, to tackle societal problems or in policymaking (exploitation).

Dissemination, as defined in the [model grant agreement of HORIZON Europe projects](#) (Annex 5), is the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium. Dissemination starts when results become available and are tailored to specific audiences. Its purpose is to transfer and circulate knowledge to enable others to work on that.

Exploitation is defined as the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating, and providing a service, or in standardization activities. Exploitation starts when the project has exploitable results with the purpose to engage the stakeholders to make a good use of the results.

Communication is defined as the strategic and targeted measure for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Communication happens through the project lifetime, starting at project's beginning. Its purpose is to inform and reach out society as a whole and show the activities performed and the use and benefits of the project for citizens.

Dissemination, exploitation, and communication are summarized in Table 1 and may be compared for a clear understanding of each of them, as they have different purposes, objectives, outputs, moments of action and target audiences.

The DEC objectives, as stated in the **WASTELESS** GA are listed as follows:

- (i) Collaborate with existing and ongoing initiatives for engagement, outreach, and impact throughout food systems.
- (ii) Conceive, implement, and update a living DEC strategy.
- (iii) Create and publish DC materials and content to raise awareness, share results and foster interactions.
- (iv) Develop and realize targeted face-to-face and online learning on FLW measurement tools to create a pool of informed and confident researchers in EU-27 and beyond.
- (v) Share knowledge with user communities and Food Supply Chain (FSC) actors.
- (vi) Develop strategies for the exploitation of project results.

Table 1. Dissemination vs Exploitation vs Communication*

	Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
	Make your results public	Make concrete use of results	Promote your project and results
Why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maximize results' impact. ▪ Allow other researchers to go a step forward. ▪ Contribute to the advancement of the State of Art. ▪ Make scientific results a common good. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lead to new legislation or recommendations. ▪ For the benefit of innovation, the economy, and the society. ▪ Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Engage with stakeholders. ▪ Attract the best experts to the team. ▪ Generate market demand. ▪ Raise awareness of how public money is spent. ▪ Show the success of European collaboration.
How	Publishing results on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Scientific magazines, ▪ Scientific or targeted conferences ▪ Databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software. ▪ Sharing knowledge, skills, data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Having a well-designed strategy ▪ Conveying clear messages. ▪ Using the right media channels.
When	At any time, as soon as the project has results	Towards the end and beyond, as soon as the project has exploitable results	From the start of the project until the end
Who	Scientists and others that can learn with the results: researchers, authorities, industry, policymakers, private sectors of interest, civil society	Scientists and others that can make good use of results: researchers, authorities, industrial authorities, policymakers, private sectors of interest, civil society	Multiple audiences: citizens, media, stakeholders

* <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/Communication,DisseminationandExploitation-2021.pdf>

3. Project outcomes

The DEC strategy of WASTELESS is closely related to the activities and outcomes of the project. For each WP specific outcomes, as derived from the grant agreement, were formulated and will be part of the DEC activities from the start until the end of the project.

3.1 Work Package 1 – Transversal community of practice and framework for measurement and monitoring of FLW

3.1.1 Objectives

WP1 aims at providing a baseline framework for the implementation of measuring and monitoring. It will investigate what are the current practices for measuring and monitoring FLW at all levels of the FSC. It will also explore the drivers and barriers of these current practices and, eventually, develop an improved framework for FLW measuring and monitoring.

3.1.2 Expected outcomes

- i) White book for FLW reduction, measurement, and monitoring practices
- ii) Report on improved framework for FLW measurement and monitoring
- iii) Framework for activities criteria
- iv) Policy briefs for experts and policy makers

3.2 Work Package 2 – Development of digital tools and methodologies

3.2.1 Objectives

This WP2 gathers the activities of Research and Development (RD) for the WASTELESS set of digital solutions and methodologies for FLW measurement and monitoring at specific stages of the FSC. Constant feedback loop will be implemented with the pilot case study leaders of WP3 for tools and methods.

3.2.2 Expected outcomes

- i) Electronic registry
- ii) Image analysis
- iii) AI model
- iv) Surplus tool
- v) Automatic system

3.3 Work Package 3 – Testing of the tools and methodologies in various case studies across the FSC

3.3.1 Objectives

In WP3 the solutions developed in WP2 will be tested in complementary operational environments of the food system. Different EU countries and sectoral contexts will be considered, as case studies will occur in 8 territories of France, Spain, Hungary, Italy, Estonia, Slovenia, Portugal, and Turkey and with

Primary producers, Agri-Food Industrials, Food retailers, Food services and Consumers. Generating data for specific food commodities and products: fruits & vegetables, chicken, meat products, potato products, fruit juices, dairy, cereal products and one other defined during the project duration.

3.3.2 Expected outcomes

- i) Technical reports of the tools and guidelines
- ii) Assessment report by experts

3.4 Work Package 4 – Data collection, management, and integration

3.4.1 Objectives

The purpose of WP4 Data collection, management, and integration is to make datasets generated by WASTELESS (as) Open (as possible) and, in that endeavour, to ensure that these data are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). More specifically, WP4 will

- (i) review data(sets) generated by WP3 demo pilots and explore whether the innovative approaches deployed deliver datasets that are substantially different from existing approaches (WP1 – macrolevel) and quantify any added value (micro-level)
- (ii) engage with WP3 to ensure (collected) data can be exchanged and exploited within and amongst interoperability layers
- (iii) develop and publish guidelines for future FAIRification of FLW data, based on best practice, and support open science publication of WP3 datasets as key exploitable results
- (iv) develop a protocol for populating the Joint Research Centre (JRC) model

3.4.2 Expected outcomes

- i) WASTELESS data collection, interoperability, and governance plan
- ii) Conversion of data collected into coefficient usable by JRC model and Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) model

3.5 Work Package 5 – Strategic actions for FLW reduction

3.5.1 Objectives

The objective of WP5 is to develop and demonstrate FLW reduction actions based on the FW hotspots identified through our case studies. Particularly developing solutions to fully utilise food losses and industrial wastes measured in the previous work packages generating value from residues and waste streams that would otherwise be lost.

3.5.2 Expected outcomes

- i) Guidelines for recycling actions from unavoidable FLW
- ii) Determination of shelf-life extension of food products
- iii) Launch a FoodWasteEXplorer portal

3.6 Work Package 6 – Classification of the tools, methodology and reduction actions into a systemic toolbox for replication

3.6.1 Objectives

Creating a technological, open access platform for stakeholders to measure and monitor FLW. Furthermore, as the other two work packages (WP2 and WP5) develop, this platform will be gradually fed and complemented with detailed abstracts to support better FLW measuring and monitoring.

3.6.2 Expected outcomes

- i) Report on the impact assessed for each case study
- ii) Decision support toolbox
- iii) Roadmap for data collection hub replication

3.7 Work Package 7 – Exploitation, communication, dissemination, and food system actor engagement

3.7.1 Objectives

WP7 will expand project impact through engagement and exchange with actors and user communities including consumers and civil society, and private and public actors, in FLW measurement and reduction actions. WP7 specific objectives are to:

- (i) collaborate with existing and ongoing initiatives for engagement, outreach, and impact throughout food systems
- (ii) conceive, implement, and update a living DC strategy and create and publish DC materials and content to raise awareness, share results, and foster interactions
- (iii) develop and realise targeted face-to-face and online learning on FLW measurement tools to create a pool of informed and confident researchers in EU-27 and beyond, share knowledge with user communities and actors, and develop strategies for exploitation of project results

3.7.2 Expected outcomes

- i) Knowledge sharing platform for food systems
- ii) DEC Plan
- iii) Exploitation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strategy
- iv) Website and social media

3.8 Work Package 8 – Project Management

3.8.1 Objectives

WP8 will consist in all the daily management activities of the project, internally and with the EC, including coordinating and preparing the project meetings, providing support, and generating periodic reports and monitoring the overall resources defined in the work plan, as well as managing any potential deviation that may occur from the original plan.

3.8.2 Expected outcomes

- i) Project management set of tools and strategy
- ii) Data Management Plan

4. Target groups and engagement

WASTELESS is focusing on the multi-actor approach to transform food systems with the final aim of reducing FLW at different stages of the food chain. To expand project impact WASTELESS DEC activities will address the following groups with the assigned targets.

4.1 European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies

Policymakers and food agencies from all over Europe are responsible for providing strategies and establishing high standards for all actors of the value chain. They are a key target of this project, as the focus is both on the public food system and on the private one. Local authorities (governments, city councils but also specific agencies, bodies, etc.) will be directly involved in the consultations to jointly define FLW challenges. Testimonials of these local policymakers will be collected in WP1 and WP4. Further, WASTELESS will provide them a set of standards for the tested tools as well as recommendations for a future regulatory framework for FLW reduction. WP3 will promote a sectorial alliance between different national food agencies as well as with technology providers, academia, and civil society to exchange views, collaborate, participate in network activities, and adopt and harmonize the best practices of FLW measuring and monitoring activities. **Estimated reach: 30 National Agencies or responsible organisations for FLW quantification and reporting.**

4.2 Civil Society (organisations/associations)

The Civil Society here includes European and National Food Industry Trade Associations, the Association of Agricultural and Food Cooperatives and Consumer organisations from partners countries and all over Europe. Their members are important beneficiaries of the outcomes of WASTELESS, as they face or will face the negative impact of uncontrolled FLW on their quality of life. Bottom-up approaches will ensure the inclusion of the views of local communities in WASTELESS strategies, to get a clear picture of FLW measurement needs and challenges and to jointly co-design possible solutions. Engaging with the civil society organisations will increase the number of consumers reached. **Estimated reach: 50 Trade and Consumer organisations.**

4.3 European, national, and regional private sector

Private companies in the food sector (producers, processors, distributors, and retailers) are affected by FLW, and thus constitute a target audience for WASTELESS. By having proper measurement and monitoring tools as well as strategies to reduce FLW they can lower their economic costs and negative environmental impacts. English (EN) language will be used and prioritised, yet translations to other EU languages can be done if necessary or needed by the partners. **Estimated reach: 300 hospitality & food services and retailers.**

4.4 Scientific community

Researchers working on measuring, monitoring, and reducing FLW are an important target audience of the project. WASTELESS will inform researchers on perceived system dynamics, priorities, and perceived impacts and will establish a place for collaboration and networking. Scientific evidence on the harmonized measuring and monitoring of FLW and on innovative processes and streams to valorise unavoidable FLW will boost innovation uptake. **Estimated reach: 30 universities and research institutes.**

4.5 General public

Consumers are central to achieving lower rates of food waste. WASTELESS is providing a common space for citizens to engage in joint decision-making with producers, retailers, and policymakers, through its website and Community of Practice. Consumers are a major driver for change and through active engagement WASTELESS will provide information about the main causes of food waste at the consumer level, the monitoring tools developed, and strategies needed to reach responsible consumption. Citizens will be invited to discover the WASTELESS methodology, tools and toolbox, and results, and encouraged to participate in the policy-making process. EN language will be used but translations to other EU languages included in the project are also predicted. WASTELESS must ensure the continuity of the activities and the mid-and long-term sustainability of its results once the EU funding comes to an end. Thus, the project will seek connections between the local community and private and public food system stakeholders **Estimated reach: 3000 consumers.**

4.6 Other research projects and initiatives

Past, current, and upcoming FLW Regional, National, European, and international projects and initiatives will be identified to leverage collaboration. The aim is to support user community interactions and research, to avoid duplication of efforts and to maximise exploitation of FLW measurement tools and reduction actions. WASTELESS will define synergies, will enhance the acceptability and visibility of the outcomes, and will foster their uptake. **Estimated reach: 20 coordinators of similar projects and initiatives.**

5. Dissemination and communication channels and tools

5.1 Project Visual Identity

5.1.1. Logo and branding

To ensure visibility and recognition of the WASTELESS public image and flexible representation, EuroFIR and VIMOSZ created the visual identity of the project including: the project brand book, logo (Figure 1) and templates for presentation and reports available on the [intranet \(Google drive\)](#). They will be displayed on all DEC materials as well as on the project website, social media channels and partners communication tools. The project identity is compliant with the guidance provided by the HORIZON program.

Figure 1 – Project logo

5.1.2. Formal HORIZON requirements of dissemination material

All DEC materials must acknowledge the support from the EU, including the EU emblem and the funding statement (Figure 2). They must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Research and Innovation Action (HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01) under Grant Agreement No. 101084222

Figure 2 – EU emblem and funding statement

Any DEC activities related to the project must include, when appropriate, a disclaimer. The following text can be used: *‘Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s)/consortium only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA) can be held responsible for them.’*

5.1.3. Leaflet, poster, roll-up, video, goodies

DC materials including poster, leaflet, and roll-up will be provided to all partners in a PDF printable version and placed on the website and on the [intranet \(Google drive\)](#) for being used when considered (e.g., conferences and other relevant national and international events). They will include but are not limited to an overview of the project, objectives, partners, and communication channels. The language will be EN but, if necessary, they can be translated to national languages of project partners.

WP7 leaders (IFA) will produce two promotional videos (approx. 2 minutes long): one to be launched until M12, presenting the project, objectives, partners, case studies and predicted outcomes; and a second one to be launched by M34 presenting the results achieved.

The goodies (type and numbers) will be decided by each partner depending on the event and type of audience and designed using the project’s brand book. The WP7 can provide support.

5.2 Virtual performance

5.2.1 Website

The project [Website](#) (domain wastelesseu.com) was developed by VIMOSZ and was officially launched in March 2023 (M3). It enhances the visibility and communication about the project by including information about the project itself, the partners of the consortium, project results (including the developed tools and methods, conceptual, guidelines, etc.), news and upcoming events, case studies, blog post in connection with FLW, other related links and information and more. Other resources will be identified and added as necessary and distributed through beneficiaries according to the project development. The website has many different subpages and functions to satisfy all the needs the project requires. This will create a strong online presence for WASTELESS, will contribute to a low carbon footprint by avoiding unnecessary printed versions of the publications and will follow the sustainability standards of the present. The design of the website follows the concept of the brand book so that it is coherent with the project's visual identity. The website structure consists of the following pages and subpages: Home, About, Partners, Outcomes (Tools, Case studies, Publications), Community (Blog, Trainings, Newsroom), Knowledge Sharing Platform and Contact. On all pages the following are included: Twitter feed, EU funding acknowledgment, Copyrights as well as different tabs to access other information. The website will be maintained for at least three years after the project ends to ensure its sustainability and VIMOSZ will be the responsible partner. The website was described in detail in the [deliverable 7.7 Website and social media](#) (M3).

5.2.2 Social media

VIMOSZ has created the Social Media (SoMe) accounts of the project to: i) communicate to a wider and diverse audience than the predefined target groups; ii) raise the profile of the project; iii) publicise project developments; iv) engage in dialogue; v) build relationships with others in the field; vi) and monitor what is being said about WASTELESS and related issues. The SoMe accounts [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#) and Research Gate were selected in agreement with the coordinator and the WP7 involved partners. LinkedIn is used by most of the people from the business world, Twitter mainly lets their users uncover new content and trending news in their area of interest and Research Gate is used by a large community of researchers. However, Research Gate has announced in February 2023 that projects will be discontinued from 31st March 2023, and thus despite mentioned in the grant agreement and selected by the coordinator and partners involved in WP7 it was not possible to use. Facebook was also mentioned in the grant agreement but was unanimously voted by the coordinator and partners involved in WP7 not to be used since in the latest years it focuses on making connections with family, friends, and people. The SoMe accounts were also described in detail in the [deliverable 7.7 Website and social media](#) (M3).

5.2.3. Knowledge sharing platform

WASTELESS will use the [Sustainable Food Systems Innovation Platform](#) as an online environment to share knowledge on food systems and raise awareness about the project among different stakeholders. WASTELESS is one of the projects managing (through IFA) the platform and will ensure its regular update. At this moment there are 4 projects managing the platform and more than 3 as contributors including the sister project FOLOU. The platform is opened to all users interested to find information about projects' case studies and their outcomes, innovations, initiatives, publications and weblinks related to sustainable foods and to similar projects and initiatives as well as all the publicly

available project results: best practices, guidelines, tools, and methodologies. The platform will be described in detail in deliverable 7.1 - Knowledge sharing platforms for food systems (Due M18).

5.2.4. Community of practice

A Community of Practice (CoP) including European and national Food Industry Trade Associations, Association of Agricultural and Food Cooperatives, and National Food Agencies from every European Member States (MS) will be established (Task 1.4). The CoP will foster the exchange of views and adoption of best practice on FLW measuring and monitoring strategies, for their harmonisation, and promote collaboration and networking between competent authorities. The CoP will be used to reach the relevant contacts at national and European level, who will be actively involved in two thematic round tables where innovative discussion training methods at various levels (e.g. national/regional/stage of the food chain) will be used to publicise project policy recommendations. The results will be reported in D1.4 CoP and replication at MS level (M36).

5.2.5. e-learning platform

WASTELESS will have a dedicated space on the [IFA e-learning platform](#), developed based on the Moodle system. The platform will host all trainings developed in the project (see section 5.4.3) and can be accessed by all interested parties upon registration. IFA will manage the platform.

5.2.6. Zenodo community

WASTELESS has a [Zenodo](#) community where scientists can upload their outputs in different forms (publications, datasets, posters, figures, etc.). By using [Zenodo](#) the project will be in line with the EU's open science initiative. EuroFIR oversees managing the [Zenodo](#) community and all partners will be informed to add their outputs, when public, to the WASTELESS community.

5.3. Publications, articles, and media dissemination

5.3.1. Blog

WASTELESS has implemented a Blog as an interactive part between all audiences. It will be user-generated and like a knowledge hub with high-quality articles full of expertise on specific topics related to the project. It will be hosted on the website as part of the CoP and managed by VIMOSZ with the support of IFA, EuroFIR and Europatat. Partners will be stimulated to engage and participate actively in creating content on alternative moments. As WASTELESS aims for quality rather than quantity each partner through their DEC responsible must submit a maximum of 4 articles a year. The DEC responsible contact of each partner can be found in this [table](#) on the [intranet \(Google Drive\)](#). The WASTELESS blog will also include news from all over the world referring to: explanation of a new phenomenon, trends and developments, strategies, and others related to the FLW and overall food & beverage sector. Further, the articles will be encouraged to be about best practices, advice, and knowledge about FLW and all its aspects.

5.3.2 Newsletter

WASTELESS will prepare a Newsletter (2 *per* year) which will include five sections: coordinator report, opinion article (written by an invited guest), case studies updates, news and events, and networking (including the updates of the sister project and another invited project). IFA, VIMOSZ, UTAD and Europatat are involved in writing and sending the newsletter. The electronic newsletter will have a

mail format (<https://mailchimp.com>) and will be distributed as widely as possible starting with the project partners and their network. It will be made available on the website where interested people can also read it and subscribe to receive it.

5.3.3. News for the written media, radio, and TV

Here press releases and briefings for the electronic and print media are included. VIMOSZ will lead this and prepare them, with special attention at the project start, midterm and end but also coinciding with other noteworthy project activities and milestones. People can find these contents on the website as well.

5.3.4. Scientific papers and publications in technical magazine

Scientific papers and publications in technical magazines resulted from the WASTELESS project need to comply with the [Standard Operation Procedures \(SOPs\)](#) approved by the coordinator. The SOPs, can be found on the [intranet \(Google drive\)](#), are intended to provide support to all partners as they incorporate guidance on authorship, acknowledgement, confidentiality, notification, and reporting of publications as well as some good practices. The Open Science policy should always be considered.

5.3.5. Practice abstracts

In total 12 practice abstracts are foreseen to be released throughout the project (WP6), 6 at M18 (D6.2) and 6 at M32 (D6.3). They will follow the common format of [EIP-AGRI](#) (The agricultural European Innovation Partnership) and will be dedicated both to specialists in the field, as well as to the public. Practice abstracts will include classified tools to measure FLW and best practises to reduce FLW, as well as the context, sources, factors, indicators, and other characteristics influencing in which case a particular best practice should be implemented. The abstracts will include an ontological representation of this classification framework designed to make it computer-understandable and reusable beyond the project.

5.4. Events

5.4.1. European, national, and regional dissemination events

Here conferences, workshops, seminars, and side events focusing on FLW topics organised at European level or in the countries of partners are included. It is foreseen for the WASTELESS partners to attend, through the lifetime of the project, to a minimum of 30 outreach events at EU and national level. As an example, Food4Future (Bilbao) or Free from Expo (Barcelona or Amsterdam) will be good dissemination opportunities to engage with a particular audience and present relevant project outcomes. Many other events focusing on FLW topics may be selected by the partners, however the coordinator must be informed in advance.

5.4.2. Discussion forum and workshops

A Discussion forum (online) will be organised after M12, to share scientific advances of the project. This forum will be organised by the coordinator (UTAD) and will be addressed to all interested target groups in the food sector, described in section 4. The discussion forum will be followed by short hands-on workshops to promote interactions with the target groups and to enhance impact.

5.4.3. Trainings

Training for food actors and community engagement monitoring will be conceived and developed by IFA, EUROFIR, VIMOSZ, and CTIC CITA starting at M12 of the project. They will have the form of eLearning(s), made available on the [IFA Moodle site](#) and geared towards different target groups: i) civil society and general public with lessons organised into 'microlearning' sessions of 5 to 10 minutes which, when accumulated, can lead to a certificate. Topics could include e.g. ways to measure FLW, how to reduce FLW for retailers, consumers, etc, ii) for scientific community and private sector as demonstration of measurement tools developed in WASTELESS shared in a train-the-trainer format to create a pool of trained researchers from throughout EU-27 (cooperation with WP3), iii) for civil society and general public as a teacher resource pack based on graphics (friendly for many languages) which can be tested in schools in the seven WP3 demonstrator countries. The trainings could be linked to FARM2FORK workshops and focus groups geared toward different subpopulations of civil society. The results also including feedback from participants will be reported in detail in D7.3. Report of learning outcomes (M34).

5.4.4. WASTELESS final conference

The WASTELESS final conference will be organised as standalone event by UTAD with the contribution of all WP leaders. In this event the WASTELESS results will be presented to the main target audience including national governments, the EC, Industrial and Professional Associations, the research community, and the press.

5.5. Partners' own dissemination channels

All the partners will contribute to promoting the project and sharing the collected and generated knowledge by using their own DC channels and tools like website, mailing lists, newsletters, social media, and events. All these activities need to be reported in the [DEC Reporting document](#). WASTELESS provides partners with all the necessary information to be able to print out physical promotional materials to increase the reach in other events and appearances.

5.6. Dissemination activities in cooperation with sister project and similar projects

WASTELESS will collaborate in DC activities with other HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK projects including the sister project FOLOU, and other similar projects from other actions and calls (Table 2). This will allow to reach a wider audience, avoid duplication of efforts and sharing knowledge amongst the projects. A FARM2FORK action plan with the sister project was already established by UTAD (M3). Contribution to the Knowledge Sharing Platform, writing articles for the blog, including updates in WASTELESS newsletter, and organising joint workshops on common topics are some activities which will be done in collaboration with these projects as part of the DEC strategy.

Table 2. Similar projects with WASTELESS

Project	Full title	Funding scheme	End date
FOLOU	Bringing knowledge and consensus to prevent and reduce food loss at the primary production stage. Understanding, measuring, training and adopting	HORIZON	31/12/2026
CULTIVATE	Co-designing food sharing innovation for food resilience	HORIZON	31/12/2026
TONOWASTE	Towards a new zero food waste mindset based on holistic assessment	HORIZON	31/08/2026
CHORIZO	Changing practices and habits through Open, responsible, and social Innovation towards zero food waste	HORIZON	30/09/2025
SISTERS	Systemic innovations for a sustainable reduction of the European food wastage	H2020	30/04/2026
BBTWINS	Agri-Food value chain digitalization for resource efficiency	H2020	31/05/2025
LOWINFOOD	Evaluating selected innovations for food waste reduction in the EU	H2020	28/02/2025
Waste2Func	Lactic acid and biosurfactants sourced from sustainable agricultural and industrial (food) WASTE feedstocks as novel functional ingredients for consumer products	H2020	30/11/2024
Agro2Circular	Territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of most relevant residues in the agri-food sector	H2020	30/09/2024
FOODRUS	Circular solutions for resilient food systems	H2020	30/04/2024
Model2BIO	Modelling tool for giving value to agri-food residual streams in bio-based industries	H2020	31/10/2023
NewFeed	Turn food industry by-products into secondary feedstuffs via circular-economy schemes	PRIMA	30/06/2025
Nano4Fresh	Nanomaterials for an environmentally friendly and sustainable handling of perishable products	PRIMA	30/11/2023

6. Key project messages

WASTELESS has defined different key messages, tailored to different target groups and to the channels and tools used to communicate and disseminate them (Table 3). The key messages are defined according to the GA, as understood by the authors of this document in M6 of the project. They are referring to the overall project context, objectives, and outcomes, and are formulated in clear and concise statements. The goal is to use these messages to attract and to engage with a higher audience in following WASTELESS project activities and outcomes. The key messages will be reviewed and updated (M18) according to the audience and DEC activity. The same message may be targeted to more than one group and may be sent more than once during the project lifetime. Partners are also encouraged to use these in their communication about the project with local, regional, and national stakeholders.

Table 3. Key messages tailored to specific target audiences (section 4) and DC channels and tools (section 5) selected to circulate them.

Key message	Target audience	Channels and tools
WASTELESS aims to develop tools and recommendations for measuring, monitoring and ultimately reducing FLW by at least 20% annually.	all	all
WASTELESS will contribute to achieve ‘Farm2Fork’ objectives and targets of the ‘European Green Deal’.	all	all
WASTELESS has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Research and Innovation Action (HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01) under Grant Agreement No. 101084222.	all	all
WASTELESS will carry out case studies to understand utilisation and role/contribution of specific food groups	all	all

such as fruits and vegetables, fruit juices, processed meat, dairy products, and cereals.		
WASTELESS will establish a unified and effective approach to FLW measurement and monitoring applicable to both public and private sectors. (WP1)	all	all
WASTELESS will contribute to the establishment of sustainable food systems and support global commitments to minimize food waste. (WP1)	all	all
WASTELESS will identify and review key drivers and barriers of existing practices of FLW measurement and monitoring. (WP1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • Civil Society • European, national, and regional private sector • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will develop an enhanced framework for measuring and monitoring FLW. (WP1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • Civil Society • European, national, and regional private sector • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will foster a collaborative CoP to encourage knowledge-sharing and cooperation among diverse stakeholders, ultimately improving FLW reduction policies and strategies throughout European MS. (WP1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • Newsletter • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
Technology will be used to develop a non-invasive artificial intelligence tool for processing FLW related data, collected from available databases. (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Society • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will develop an innovative system for tracking and measuring FLW produced by the stakeholders. (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Society • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will develop a Blockchain strategy in line with EU policies, for the quantification and mapping of FLW. (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will set up new criteria for the classification, measurement, and mapping of FLW based on the Lan sink's ladder. (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
The Blockchain strategy developed will enable the efficiency of the company's production system. (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will make possible the increase of economic sustainability of the food shopping experience through a reduction in the cost of certain products, as well as the improvement of environmental and social impacts of food waste. (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Society • European, national, and regional private sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • Blog • Newsletter • Events
The innovative tools to monitor and measure FLW will be tested on real environment covering the whole FSC: food industries, food retailers, food services, households and selected food supply chains. (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Society • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community • General Public • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will collect and analyse data to identify the main FLW drivers and draw a map of best practices towards the zero waste Horizon goal. (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
Innovative technological applications that generate added value products from residues and waste streams will be available. (WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects

New developed products will be integrated in the European context based on regulatory frameworks. (WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will improve and upgrade the Food Waste Explorer database information. (WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • CoP • Events • Similar projects
WASTELESS will facilitate abstract integration and data standardization leveraging common format and representation. (WP6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • CoP • Events • Similar projects
A systemic user-friendly toolbox for replication of FLW reduction actions and methodologies will be developed. (WP6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional policymakers, and food agencies • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community • Other research projects and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will provide access to an open platform for stakeholders monitoring FLW. (WP6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional private sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • Newsletter • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
Knowledge and tools will be open and made available to the communities and all actors of the FSC. (WP7)	all	all
Innovative trainings about the developed tools will be provided to create a pool of informed and confident researchers in EU-27 and beyond. (WP7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European, national, and regional private sector • Scientific community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • SoMe • KSP • CoP • Zenodo • Blog • Newsletter • Written media, radio, and TV • Scientific papers • Events • Partner's DC • Similar projects
WASTELESS will efficiently communicate, exploit, and disseminate all project activities and results. (WP8)	• all	• all
Innovation activities deployed under WASTELESS will be implemented in an efficiently and timely manner. (WP8)	• all	• all

7. Exploitation Strategy

WASTELESS project is expected to deliver several innovations including new tools, models, and standardisation protocols to address the FLW measuring and monitoring challenges. Due to the

importance of results protection and ownership aspects, an Intellectual Property Protection Strategy (IPPS) was included in the [Consortium Agreement](#) to protect project partners' interests and set a transparency approach from the beginning, avoiding future misunderstandings and conflicts. General rules were defined as follows:

1. Each of the partners will remain the owner of its Intellectual Property (IP), which will be only shared for the development of this project but fulfilling confidentiality obligations and legitimate interests of the owner of the IP.
2. IP generated during the project (foreground IP) is owned by the partner(s) producing it. During the project, execution protection strategies will be analysed, and partners will decide the best option for protecting the IPR: Patent & Utility model, Industrial design, Copyright, Trademark, or Confidential information.
3. Fair and reasonable access terms will be used to license the required background and foreground IP to the lead exploiter, providing, if necessary, royalty payments to the IP providers proportional to their contribution.
4. Each beneficiary shall ensure that no agreements will be stipulated which are in contrast with the above- mentioned provisions to be observed by employees, service providers, suppliers, post-docs, and/or students.

From M9 to the end of the project WP4 (EuroFIR) will cover the development, execution, and supervision of plans, policies, programmes, and practices that deliver, manage, protect, and enhance value and exploitation of WASTELESS data and supporting information.

Guidelines for the exploitation and IPR strategy will be written by WP7 (JSI) from M25 and are predicted to be published at M36, D7.6 - Exploitation and IPR Strategy. These guidelines will contain description of the types of background and foreground IP of the project, and guidelines of management of IP rights, including the legal framework for managing IPR, such as agreements and contracts. The exploitation strategy will explore possibilities for commercialization of solutions developed during the project, from IP protection to promotion and potential licensing. Uncovered issues that might arise during the project will be addressed by the Advisory Board and the Innovation Management Team, composed of experts in innovation management and/or IPR from the partner organisations or external to the consortium.

8. DEC roadmap

The DEC roadmap provides a general idea of the DEC activities through the lifetime of the project. It includes 3 stages according to the project development as stated in the grant agreement. The stages are not independent of one another and may overlap.

Figure 3 – DEC roadmap

8.1. Enhance project visibility (M1-M36)

At the beginning of this stage the aim is to raise awareness of project activities, outputs, and benefits through diverse channels to all defined audiences (section 4). In this phase the DEC strategy is defined, and the project has a graphical identity, a website and social media accounts, the knowledge sharing platform was selected, the [Zenodo](#) community created, and the DEC materials produced. The target groups for this stage can also be reached through partners' own dissemination channels and connections with similar projects. Information to be disseminated during this stage includes but are not limited to project objectives and expected results, presentation of project partners and involvement in the project.

8.2. Share knowledge and tools (M7-M36)

At this stage digital tools and methodologies are developed and are tested on the case studies. The main objective of the DEC strategy here is to share the knowledge and the tools with a larger audience: civil society organisation/association, stakeholders in the private sector, the scientific community, the general public and other related projects. All communication channels will be used (section 6). The CoP on the website, including the blog and the newsroom, will be of great use. Intensive cooperation with similar projects is expected through the Knowledge Sharing Platform and the organisation of cooperative dissemination events. Information to be disseminated during this stage includes but is not limited to framework for harmonised FLW measuring and monitoring, innovative and robust tools, and methodologies.

8.3. Promote project outcomes (M24-M36)

Most project activities will be finalized in this period and the main objectives of DEC will be to promote project results, engage with all target groups (section 4), share experiences and best practices with community of actors, enlarge the user community and widen the impact of the project. The guidelines for the exploitation and IPR strategy will be written. Important outcomes to be disseminated at this stage include but are not limited to integration of the innovative tools into a bigger framework recommendation for future regulatory framework. The final WASTELESS conference will be organised at this stage.

9. Reporting, evaluation, and monitoring of DEC activities

9.1 Reporting

A [DEC Reporting document](#) was created and will be used by all partners to list all activities related to DEC. It can be found on the [Intranet \(google drive\)](#). Each member of the consortium must fill in the document whenever they make an appearance where the project was mentioned. Instructions on how to fill the document are also provided. VIMOSZ will oversee the reporting on DEC activities by the partners in due course.

9.2. Evaluation

For the evaluation procedure of DEC performance, KPIs have been formulated. The success of the project will be evaluated yearly by analysing the KPIs (Annex I). These will enable the WP7 partners to manage possible deviations and make any needed updates in a timely manner.

9.3. Monitoring

IFA and VIMOSZ will oversee the progress of DEC activities regularly by analysing the [DEC Reporting document](#), the KPIs and the overall DEC performance. In case of deviation VIMOSZ will contact and follow up with the partners in due course. The DEC Plan will be reviewed at M18 to update KPIs and adjust the plan as needed and at M36 a final report will be provided.

10. Conclusion

The major output of this deliverable is the DEC strategy including the target groups, channel and tools and the roadmap. The project will create a brand and virtual ecosystem which can outlive the duration of WASTELESS project and be a very valuable tool including useful information in the challenge to reduce FLW.

11. Annexes

Annex I – Key Performance Indicators target at M36

Name of the KPI	Target at M36	Type of data
Website		
Nº of visits	3000	Google Analytics
Nº of pages/visit	3	
Average time spent/visit (min)	2	
LinkedIn		
Nº of posts	150	HootSuite Analytics
Nº of followers	400	
Page engagement	1500	
Page clicks	1500	
Twitter		
Nº of posts	150	HootSuite Analytics
Nº of followers	400	
Post key interactions	1500	
Post traffic	1500	
Knowledge sharing platform		
Nº of visits	2500	Google analytics
Nº of pages/visit	3	
Average time spent/visit (min)	2	
E-learning platform		
Nº of courses	2	Moodle analytics
Nº trainees/course	10	
Nº of completed trainings (80%)	10	
Zenodo community		
Nº of documents	40	Zenodo analytics
Nº of visits	100	
Blog/CoP		
Nº of articles	100	Google analytics
Nº of page visits	1500	
Newsletter		
Releases	2/year	Mailchimp analytics
Nº of subscribers	100	
Nº of openings/newsletter	80	
News for the written media, radio, and TV		
Nº of news	3	DEC Reporting document
Nº of people reached	200	
Scientific papers and publications in technical magazine		
Nº of papers	10	DEC Reporting document

Practice abstracts		
Nº of practice abstracts	12	DEC Reporting document
Events		
Nº of events	10	DEC Reporting document
Nº of people reached	1000	
Discussion forum & Workshops		
Nº of discussion forum	1/4	Participant list
Nº of people reached	10/40	
Final conference		
Nº of presentations	10	Participant list
Nº of invited speakers	3	
Nº of participants	50	
Partners' own dissemination channels		
Nº of mentions (Social media, press releases, website, mailing lists, newsletters, social media, events)	100	DEC Reporting document
Nº of people reached	500	
Cooperation with sister project and similar projects		
Nº of projects invited to collaborate	20	DEC Reporting document
Nº of activities initiated	5	
Nº of people reached	500	
Other KPIs		
Nº of brochure/leaflet/goodies distributed	500	DEC Reporting document
Popular science articles	10	DEC Reporting document

Annex II – Partner’s contribution

Dissemination and communication channels and tools	Partner to contribute
Website	all
SoMe	all
KSP	UTAD, IFA, VIMOSZ, EuroFIR, Europatat, JSI
CoP	all
eLearning and training activities	IFA, VIMOSZ, EuroFIR, CTIC-CITA, WIISE
Zenodo	all
Blog	all (each 4x year)
Newsletter	all
News for media radio TV	all
Scientific papers	UTAD, Hacettepe, SDU, ISA, JSI
Practice abstracts	JSI, UTAD
European, national, and regional dissemination events	all
Discussion forum and workshops	UTAD, WP leaders
Final conference	all

